

Application and Use Cases of Blockchain Technology

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Introduction:

As Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies have been on fire for a large portion of 2017, focus has turned to blockchain, the underlying technology that powers these digital currencies. But blockchain technology has many more potential use cases and applications other than just serving as the fuel behind Bitcoin.

Discussion Topics:

Scott will discuss practical applications of Blockchain technology in a variety of industries and verticals, showcasing that blockchain and bitcoin warrant more respect than the mainstream media currently places on Bitcoin, neglecting the incredible applications of the underlying technology.

Keywords: Business, B2B, Blockchain, Cryptocurrency.

Biography:

A seasoned business strategist with a passion for bleeding edge technologies. Scott has worked with several high profile companies such as Cisco, Bell, Avaya and NEC. He has worked in the enterprise space, consulting on complex networking, telecommunication and SAAS projects. With a proficiency in project management, sales, leadership, scaling and improving operational efficiencies in F500 companies, he is an industry leader in knowledge pertaining to fintech, blockchain, and cryptocurrency